

	Data fields	Data example
General data	Title	Text
	Author(s)	First name and Family name
	Publication year	Date (e.g., 11/11/11)
	Educational institution	Name of the institution
	Country	Name of the country
	Source	Name of the source (e.g., name of the journal or conference)
	Type of study	Text (e.g., journal, conference paper)
	Abstract	Text
Research questions	Educational environment	Name of the environment (e.g., high school, higher education)
	Objective	Text
	Impact factors	Name of the factor or category
	Multilevel models	Name of the model
	Other AI techniques	Name of the technique